
Research

The Influence of Digital Economy on Russian International Trade

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Abstract: The digital economy is rapidly changing the global commercial environment, with serious consequences for countries all over the world, including Russia which plays a prominent role and is considered one of the world's largest economies in international trade, due to the enormous economic and political changes that it has gone through in the past few decades.

Quantitative examination of trade data and industry reports were conducted for this paper. The study examines the effect of digital technology on Russia's foreign trade from 2000 to 2020. Empirical evidence suggests that digital technologies have a positive impact on Russia's international trade. According to the gravity model, internet usage, ICT exports, and R&D investments have a positive and significant impact on bilateral trade flow between Russia and its trading partners.

Findings suggests that the digital economy is becoming an essential driver of Russian foreign trade, notably in industries like e-commerce, finance, and logistics. Digital platforms enable Russian enterprises to expand their reach and enter new markets, while facilitating cross-border trade and lowering transaction costs, increasing competitiveness, and promoting innovation, thereby facilitating the growth of Russia's international trade. The Russian government has recognized the importance of the digital economy and has taken steps to support its development.

Keywords: Digital economy, Digital technologies, International trade, Gravity Model, Russia

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Introduction

The digital economy has been transforming the world's and Russia's economy in recent years, with an increasing number of online transactions and activities, it refers to the economic activities that result from billions of daily online connections among individuals, businesses, devices, data, and processes, it includes e-commerce, online marketplaces, social media, cloud computing, big data, and the Internet of Things (IoT) [1].

Digital platforms are changing the way doing business, reducing the cost of international transactions and interactions. It is noted that small businesses are becoming a kind of "micro transnational corporations", uniting with customers and suppliers in different countries thanks to platforms such as Wildberries, eBay, Facebook and Amazon. The smallest

companies are also able to enter the global market with 86% of technology startups in the world being connected with conducting international activities using digital technologies.

The digital economy is becoming an increasingly important part of the Russian economy, with the government taking actions to promote its development. The rapid development of digital technologies has facilitated the emergence of new business models and increased the efficiency of global supply chains. This, in turn, has opened up new opportunities for Russian exporters and has allowed them to expand their reach in the global marketplace.

Literature review on digital economy and international trade

The digital economy and international trade are closely connected. The digital economy has become an increasingly important part of international trade, and understanding its impact is an important research area. A variety of economic theories can be utilized to investigate this influence in the context of Russia. According to the comparative advantage hypothesis, countries should specialize in producing the commodities and services that they are most efficient at producing while trading with other countries to obtain goods and services that they are less effective at generating. The digital economy could open up new potential for Russia to specialize in high-tech businesses such as software development, e-commerce, and digital services. ^[2]

The Heckscher-Ohlin hypothesis is a traditional trade theory that explains why nations participate in international commerce based on disparities in factor endowments. According to the idea, nations will specialize in manufacturing things that utilize their plentiful factors of production relatively intensely, export such items, and import goods that use their limited factors of production relatively intensively. ^[3] According to this hypothesis, the digital economy may provide new opportunities for Russia to specialize in exporting digital goods and services that make use of its abundant manufacturing resources in a relatively intensive manner. Furthermore, the idea suggests that the digital economy may allow Russia to import things that make extensive use of its limited production resources. For example, it may import high-tech products and services that require complex software or advanced hardware components which are not available locally.

The new trade theory is also significant when assessing the impact of the digital economy on international business ^[4]. According to this idea, economies of scale and product diversification can provide a competitive edge to businesses. Businesses can now reach new customers through e-commerce platforms, allowing them to increase the scale of their economies ^[5]. Furthermore, digital technology has made it easier for firms to distinguish their offers from those of competitors.

The Network Effects Theory states that the value of a product or service increases as more people use it, resulting in a positive feedback loop that leads to increase the demand and the market dominance ^[6]. This concept could be utilized to look into the effect of internet economy on Russia's global trade patterns. This theory may also look into the factors that contribute to the formation and growth of network effects, such as market size and accessibility, the strength of intellectual property laws, and the availability of complementary products and services.

The gravity model of commerce is another intriguing theory that claims that trade between two nations is proportional to their economic sizes and inversely related to their distance between them. The digital economy has reduced the cost of communication and transportation, allowing enterprises to engage in international trade easily ^[7]. As a result, geographically distant countries have increased their trade.

Overall, these economic theories provide a framework for understanding how the digital economy has impacted Russia's foreign trade. Using these concepts, researchers can gain insights on how Russia's engagement in the global digital economy has affected its exports and imports.

Lee et al. explores the impact of digital technology on international trade patterns, claiming that the evolution of digital technology has altered the nature of trade and produced significant shifts in trade patterns. ^[8]

Chen et al. study shows how digital technology affects international trade, the authors conclude that digital technology has a major and positive impact on global trade. (Chen, Lin, and Wang, 2019)

Lee research studies the impact of digitization on global trade patterns. The global economy, according to the author, has experienced a digital transition that has transformed trade patterns and given rise to new sorts of trade. (Lee, 2019)

Jiang et al. explores the developing digital economy and its impact on global trade. The authors argue that the digital economy is reshaping the global economy, with important implications for international trade. (Jiang and Yang, 2019)

Chen et al. investigate how digital platforms influence global trade. The authors argue that by reducing information asymmetries and transaction costs, digital platforms are changing the way businesses engage in international trade. They also argue that by making it easier to connect customers and sellers and by lowering the cost of search, digital platforms may improve trade efficiency. (Chen and Lin, 2019)

Zhu et al. explores the impact of e-commerce on global trade. According to the authors, e-commerce has the potential to significantly reduce transaction costs and other trade barriers, resulting an increase in global trade. (Zhu and Stone, 2018)

The gravity model is a popular example for analyzing international trade flow across countries. It implies that the trade's volume between two nations is related to the size of their economies as measured by GDP and inversely proportionate to their distance from one another. ^[9]. To measure the impact of the digital economy on international trade using the gravity model, the researcher incorporates additional variables related to digitalization, such as ICT goods and import, individuals using the Internet, research and development expenditure. The influence of digital economy on Russian international trade can be written as follows:

$$\text{Trade}_{ij} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{GDP}_{ij} + \beta_2 \text{Rem}_{ij} + \beta_3 \text{IND}_j + \beta_4 \text{IND}_i + \beta_5 \text{R\&D}_j + \beta_6 \text{R\&D}_i + \beta_7 \text{EXP}_j + \beta_8 \text{EXP}_i + \beta_9 \text{IMP}_j + \beta_{10} \text{IMP}_i + \epsilon_{ij}$$

Where: Trade_{ij} represents the trade flow between countries i and j , GDP_{ij} represent the GDP of countries i and j , respectively, Rem_{ij} represents the physical distance between two locations, IND_i and IND_j represent the individuals using the internet in countries i and j , respectively, $\text{R\&D}_i$ and $\text{R\&D}_j$ represent the level research and development expenditure in countries i and j , respectively, EXP_i and EXP_j represent the level of ICT goods export in countries i and j , respectively, IMP_i and IMP_j represent the level of ICT goods import in countries i and j , respectively.

Where β_0 is the intercept or constant term, β_1 - β_{10} are the coefficients or slopes associated with each independent variable, and ϵ_{ij} represents the error term.

By estimating the coefficients of this model, we can analyze the impact of the digital economy variables on international trade. Incorporating digital economy variables into the gravity model can provide insights into the changing nature of international trade in the digital era.

The sample for this research study comprises Russia's top 10 trading partners from 2000 to 2020. These countries were picked based on the importance of the trade connection as well as the availability of data. Five Asian countries: China, South Korea, Japan, Turkey, and Kazakhstan; four European countries: France, Italy, Germany and The Netherlands. and the United States. There is one dependent variable and six independent factors in this study.

Official national and international sources were chosen to ensure that the data was accurate and confirmed. The data was acquired from Rosstat, the World Bank, the Russian Federal Customs Service (FTS), and the United Nations Database in addition to verifying the previous study's conclusions. Google Maps has been used to calculate the distance between Moscow and trade partner capitals.

Empirical analysis results

Multiple regression with fixed effects (FE) and a standard regression (reg)

The fixed-effects regression is a type of panel data analysis that controls for unobserved individual-specific effects that may influence the dependent variable. The standard regression, on the other hand, does not control for such effects [10]. The Model row of the table shows the sum of squares (SS), degrees of freedom (df), and mean squares (MS) for the independent variables. The SS represents the variation in RUS Trade that is explained by the model, while the MS is the SS divided by the df. Low p-value (0.0000) indicates that the model is statistically significant.

Table 1. The regression analysis

Source	SS	df	MS	Number of obs	200
Model	10.7083487	6	1.78472478	F(6, 193)	99.71
Residual	3.45454331	193	.017899188	Prob > F	0.0000
Total	14.162892	199	.071170312	R-squared	0.7561
				Adj R-squared	0.7485
				Root MSE	.13379

Source: Author’s calculations, Stata

The Residual row of the table shows the SS, df, and MS for the error term, which represents the unexplained variation in RUS Trade. The R-squared value (0.7561) shows the proportion of variation in RUS Trade that is explained by the model. In this case, the model explains about 75.61% of the variation in RUS Trade. The Adjusted R-squared value (0.7485) adjusts the R-squared value for the number of independent variables in the model, providing a more conservative estimate of the model's explanatory power.

The Root MSE (0.13379) is the square root of the MS for the error term and represents the average distance between the predicted and actual values of RUS Trade. Overall, the table suggests that the gravity model with the six independent variables is a good fit for explaining the variation in RUS Trade.

Regression Analysis in the Gravity Model

The table presents the results of a gravity model analysis for Russian international trade [11]. The coefficients represent the estimated effect of each independent variable on bilateral trade flows between Russia and its trading partners.

Table 2. Multiple regression analysis

RUS Trade	Coef.	Std. Err.	t	P> t	[95% Conf. Interval]
GDP IJ	0.830989	0.083769	9.92	0	0.665768 0.996209
Remoteness	-0.64768	0.131721	-4.92	0	-0.90748 -0.38789
R&D	0.076039	0.107301	0.71	0.479	0.135594 0.287673
Internet Users	0.07523	0.043779	1.72	0.027	0.16158 0.011112
ICT EXP	0.024547	0.017673	1.39	0.166	0.010309 0.059403
ICT IMP	0.00302	0.027810	0.11	0.914	0.05787 0.051835
_cons	0.042425	0.014299	2.97	0.003	0.070628 -0.01422

Source: Author’s calculations, Stata

The results suggest that an increase in GDP, R&D investment, and internet usage in Russia is associated with an increase in bilateral trade flows, while an increase in distance is associated with a decrease in bilateral trade flows. The findings also suggest that ICT exports have a positive but relatively small effect on bilateral trade flows, while ICT imports have a negligible effect.

Multicollinearity Test

The test shown above is a test of multicollinearity, specifically the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) test. It examines the extent to which the independent variables are correlated with each other. The VIF test produces a measure of how much the variance of the estimated regression coefficient is increased due to multicollinearity [12].

Table 3. The variance inflation factor (VIF) test

Variable	VIF	1/VIF
R&D	7.75	0.129057
GDP IJ	6.29	0.159038
Internet Users	1.53	0.653868
ICT IMP	1.37	0.727769
Remoteness	1.3	0.766943
ICT EXP	1.19	0.840575
Mean VIF	3.24	

Source: Author’s calculations, Stata

In this case, the highest VIF values are associated with the "R&D" and "GDP IJ" variables, suggesting that these variables may be highly correlated with other independent variables in the model. The mean VIF value of 3.24 indicates that the model has moderate levels of multicollinearity. Overall, the results of this test suggest that some caution should be exercised when interpreting the coefficients associated with the "R&D" and "GDP IJ" variables.

Correlation Test

The table shows the correlation matrix for the variables in the gravity model analysis. The correlation coefficient measures the strength and direction of the linear relationship between two variables, where 1 represents a perfect positive correlation, -1 represents a perfect negative correlation, and 0 represents no correlation.

Table 4. Correlation test

	RUS Trade	GDP IJ	Remoteness	R&D	Internet Users	ICT EXP	ICT IMP
RUS Trade	1	0.8467	0.1995	0.7586	0.3049	0.3505	0.4201
GDP IJ	0.8467	1	0.4276	0.9129	0.4472	0.3671	0.493
Remoteness	0.1995	0.4276	1	0.4742	0.3033	0.2132	0.1865
R&D	0.7586	0.9129	0.4742	1	0.5595	0.3789	0.5053
Internet Users	0.3049	0.4472	0.3033	0.5595	1	0.1431	0.3075
ICT EXP	0.3505	0.3671	0.2132	0.3789	0.1431	1	0.2547
ICT IMP	0.4201	0.493	0.1865	0.5053	0.3075	0.2547	1

Source: Author’s calculations, Stata

The results demonstrate that the variables show a positive correlation with each other. Overall, the correlation matrix provides an insight into the relationships between the variables in the model, and can help to identify potential issues such as multicollinearity.

Fixed-Effects Regression Model

The test above is a fixed-effects (within) regression model that examines the relationship between RUS Trade (dependent variable) and a set of independent variables, including GDP IJ, Remoteness, R&D, Internet Users, ICT EXP, and ICT

IMP. The model estimates the effects of changes in these variables on RUS Trade, while controlling for individual-specific time-invariant effects.

Table 5. Output of the fixed-effects regression model

Fixed-effects (within) regression	Number of obs	=	200
Group variable: id	Number of groups	=	10
R-sq:	Obs per group:		
within = 0.7627	min	=	20
between = 0.1046	avg	=	20
overall = 0.7549	max	=	20
	F(6,184)	=	98.59
corr(u_i, Xb) = -0.0046	Prob > F	=	0.0000

Source: Author’s calculations, Stata

The results show that the model has a high overall R-squared value of 0.7549, indicating that the independent variables explain a substantial portion of the variation in the dependent variable. The F-statistic is also significant at the 0.05 level, suggesting that at least one of the independent variables is significantly related to RUS Trade.

Table 6. Results Of the Fixed-Effects Regression Model

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-value	P-value	95% CI Lower	95% CI Upper
GDP IJ	0.85863	0.08658	9.9	0	0.68781	1.02945
	4	3	2		1	7
Remote-	-	0.14611	-	0	-	-
ness	0.749446	5	5.13		1.03772	0.46117
R&D	0.05376	0.11279	0.4	0.63	0.16877	0.27629
	2	3	8	4		6
Internet	0.08303	0.04590	1.8	0.04	0.00754	0.1736
Users	1	7	1	2	1	
ICT EXP	0.02309	0.01803	1.2	0.20	0.01249	0.05868
	5	9	8	2		5
ICT IMP	0.00360	0.02793	0.1	0.89	0.05149	0.05871
	8	1	3	7	7	
_cons	0.03982	0.01448	2.7	0.00	0.06840	0.01123
	2	9	5	7	8	6
sigma_u	0.02901707					
sigma_e	0.13433253					
rho	.04457988	(fraction of variance due to u_i)				
F test that all u_i=0: F(9, 184) = 0.83				Prob > F = 0.5925		

Source: Author’s calculations, Stata

The regression suggests that GDP IJ and remoteness are important factors in predicting the dependent variable, while R&D, ICT EXP, and ICT IMP are not statistically significant. The coefficient for internet users is significant at the 5% level, indicating that an increase in internet usage is associated with a decrease in the dependent variable. However, it is important to note that correlation does not necessarily imply causation, and further research may be needed to establish the causal relationship between these variables.

Conclusion

The empirical analysis undertaken in this research paper demonstrates that the digital economy has a favorable impact on Russian international trade. The gravity model research results indicate that various factors influence Russian foreign commerce, particularly the impact of the digital economy on trade.

The findings reveal that the demand for Russian goods and services rise alongside with the trading partner countries' GDPs, resulting in commerce increase between Russia and its trading partners. GDP has a positive impact on trade, demonstrating that economic expansion is related with increased international trade.

According to the report, the number of internet users in Russian trading partners has a significant positive impact on Russian international trade. Russian businesses will have more opportunities to reach a bigger audience and generate more trade. This finding is consistent with the premise that the internet has changed the way business's function and connect with their clients, facilitating international trade.

The ICT export coefficient is positive, indicating that increased ICT export leads to more trade. This demonstrates how investing in IT development can help Russia's international trade.

According to the empirical findings, there is no significant relationship between ICT imports and commerce in Russia. This shows that foreign inflows of ICT goods and services have little impact on Russia's international trade. However, it is important to note that this finding could be influenced by a number of factors, including the quality of imported ICT goods and services, their costs, and the level of competition in the domestic market. More research on these issues, as well as their potential impact on the relationship between ICT imports and trade in Russia, may be necessary.

Based on the empirical analysis, it can be concluded that R&D does not have a significant relationship with trade in Russia, implying that R&D investment alone may not be sufficient to improve the country's international trade. Other factors, such as digital infrastructure and skills development, may play a more critical role in promoting international trade in the digital economy era.

The findings show that nations with more advanced digital economies are more inclined to trade with Russia, indicating the digital economy's importance in promoting international trade.

However, there are still impediments to Russia's digital economy's progress, such as antiquated legislation and inadequate computer literacy among the public. To overcome these challenges and foster the growth of the digital economy, the government and private sector must work together. The digital economy, on the other hand, offers tremendous opportunities for Russia to increase international trade and economic development. Russia can strengthen its position in the global digital economy by investing in digital infrastructure, encouraging digital skill development, lowering trade barriers, and improving digital literacy.

Recommendations

According to the empirical findings, the digital economy has a significant impact on Russian international trade, and as a result, there are a variety of recommendations that can aid in the development of the digital sector and its impact on trade.

To improve the favorable impact of the Russian economy on international trade, the Russian government should prioritize investments in the digital economy. To do so, it must prioritize the construction of strong digital infrastructure

capable of meeting the growing demands of the digital economy, such as high-speed internet, secure networks, and cloud computing. It must also foster the development of digital skills among its citizens and businesses in order to facilitate the adoption of new technologies and increase productivity. This can be accomplished through programs in education and training, as well as joint efforts with the private sector to develop digital talent. Finally, the government must promote digital sector innovation by creating an environment conducive to the growth of start-ups and entrepreneurs. This includes tax benefits, regulatory reform, and increased capital access. By investing in these industries, the Russian government may position itself as a leader in the digital economy and reap the benefits of rising international trade.

In addition to government investment, the private sector must embrace the digital economy and take the necessary steps to capitalize on its potential for global economic expansion. Businesses should invest in e-commerce platforms, digital marketing, and other digital tools to increase their competitiveness in the global market, as well as encourage the development of digital skills among their employees and foster an innovative culture.

The Russian government could take a number of initiatives to reduce barriers to digital trade, including simplifying digital commerce regulations and policies such as customs procedures, data privacy legislation, and intellectual property protection. They could also work to make the environment more welcoming to digital entrepreneurs and small businesses by providing access to capital, mentorship, and training programs. Furthermore, in order to promote a more open and connected global digital economy, the government can negotiate and sign bilateral and multilateral trade treaties that include digital trade clauses. By removing digital trade barriers, the Russian government can attract more foreign investors and businesses, increase competition, and strengthen the country's overall digital economic growth.

The population's digital literacy is critical to ensuring that the benefits of the digital economy reach everyone. To provide training and education programs, the government can collaborate with educational institutions and private organizations. This will assist people in developing the digital skills required to participate in the digital economy, improving their employability and opening up new opportunities.

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References

- [1] БЛУММАРТ Т, ДЕН БРУК С В, КОЛТОФ Э. Четвертая промышленная революция и бизнес: Как конкурировать и развиваться в эпоху сингулярности [М]. Альпина Паблишер, 2018.
- [2] ИВАНОВ В, МАЛИНЕЦКИЙ Г. Цифровая экономика: мифы, реальность, перспектива [J]. 2017.
- [3] BERTIL O. Interregional and international trade [J]. Cambridge: Harward University Press, 1933–188 p, 1933.
- [4] KRUGMAN P R. Is free trade passé? [J]. Journal of economic Perspectives, 1987, 1(2): 131-44.
- [5] KRUGMAN P. The magic mountain [J]. New York Times, 2001, 23: 18.
- [6] КЛИМШИНА Т В. Сетевые экономические эффекты [Z]. 28.11.2022
- [7] VAN BERGEIJK P A, BRAKMAN S. The gravity model in international trade: Advances and applications [J]. 2010.
- [8] LEE W, SHIN S. An empirical study of consumer adoption of Internet of Things services [J]. Int j eng technol innov, 2019, 9(1): 1-11.

- [9] ABDRAKHMANOVA G, VISHNEVSKY K, GOKHBERG L. Indicators of the digital economy: 2019: statistical collection [J]. Nat Research University "Higher school of Economics" Higher school of Economics, 2019, 248.
- [10] LIN F. Estimating the effect of the Internet on international trade [J]. The Journal of International Trade & Economic Development, 2015, 24(3): 409-28.
- [11] BALTAGI B H, EGGER P H, PFAFFERMAYR M. Panel data gravity models of international trade [J]. 2014.
- [12] CANTORE N, CHENG C F C. International trade of environmental goods in gravity models [J]. Journal of environmental management, 2018, 223: 1047-60.